

SQL SPECIFICATIONS FOR DATA ANALYSIS.

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INTRODUCTION

the world in experience higher of education important from the goals one is this students professional develop their _ to know skills formation and received knowledge , skill , qualification and competencies to life practical apply technologies app done _

As you know , teaching tools - training process organize reach main from the elements one is considered The main task of the teacher to students own the subject interesting by doing show and that's it with together students to science has been interests from increase consists of In this place of teaching modern technical and software of means to use right will come . Modern multimedia from technologies use of the teacher pedagogical skills , technological opportunities more expands .

Modern information and communication technologies opportunities very wide system to him _ _ known has been computer , multimedia tools , computer networks , such as the Internet from concepts except series new concepts are also included . To these information systems , information systems management , information transmission systems , data warehouse , information warehouse manage systems , knowledge warehouse etc example to be possible

Data analysis to do SQL properties for .

Basically SQL is relational to algebra based on huge data bases records collection releases _ SELECT is basic SQL , records , columns / attributes , calculations , grouping _ and etc filtering for strong clauses with provided . of SQL (Michael Stonebraker one times SQL intergalactic data speaking called the language) big popularity basically his high level with the syntax (no). depends _ programming many requests for necessary) and him the work from the desktop (Access). open source (MySQL, PostgreSQL) and to commercial (Oracle, IBM DB2, Microsoft SQL Servers) . has been all kind of Information base manage in systems done increase for is necessary . Wide acceptance ANSI and _ different national agencies SQL standardization by ISO with help gave _ The first SQL standard was 1986 (ANSI) and 1989 (ISO), then and in 1992 , 1999, 2003, 2008 and 2011 publication done _

Previous in the department as mentioned in SQL queries result (select commands) data based on (mainly table or in view) to be stored / stored maybe , but data from the base different goals and to formats , that is another data to the base export to be done can _ , Excel/CSV file , text file , HTML, ODBC/JDBC data source and others _

But SELECT statements just data from the base information separate get and filtering with is not limited . His different clauses all the result lines or groups or rows for (GROUP BY and HAVING clauses) . different processing to give duties perform can _

First since the standard (1986/1989) , all SQL dialects self descriptive names with (statistical) aggregate called functions _ main statistics functions done increased : SUM, COUNT, AVG, MIN, MAX.

since 1999 since SQL standards the most important from the goals one is mainly OLAP (On Line Analytical Processing) features (sometimes mirror also called functions) via information analysis is to do Dialects between In OLAP some differences there is . Data analysis to do for the richest DBMSs are Oracle and DB2, open coded systems while less is generous . But some one basic OLAP operations , such as ranking , wide spread _ An example for , PostgreSQL 's current version (9.3) is different functions RANK , DENSE_RANK, PERCENT_RANK, CUME_DIST, LEAD, LAG, NTILE, NTH_VALUE and others uses _ Some advanced SQL OLAP functions for next to the department see _

Less so in SQL known and applied common statistics procedures for statistics are functions . More commercial data base servers (Oracle, DB2, SQL Server) eng good statistics features with provided . With that together , open source servers STDEV_POP (population standard deviation), STDEV_SAMP (sample for standard deviation) CORR (correlation), COVAR_POP (population covariance), COVAR_SAMP (sample covariance), as REGR_INTERCEPT (y intercept) . useful functions present is enough (x,y) pairs with determined the most small into squares suitable linear equation), REGR_SLOPE (eng small into squares suitable linear of Eq slope), PostgreSQL (2013).

Commercial data base of servers main representative as Oracle too a lot statistics features with provided . Theirs most are Oracle SQL core dialect included , but such as Oracle Data Mining and Oracle R Enterprise another extensions there is . Oracle data base documents According to Oracle (2013), available has been main statistics options :

- Descriptive statistics ;
- Hypothesis check _
- Correlation analysis (parametric and parametric did not exist);
- Rating functions ;
- Xi is the square statistics with mutually activity tables ;
- Linear regression ;
- ANOVA;
- Test distribution suitability ;
- Window Aggregate functions ;
- Statistics aggregates ;
- LAG/LEAD functions ;
- Aggregate functions about report to give

Information bases and again one excitement : NoSQL. Information base the world usually last ten in annuals as a peaceful place seen _ This of the field main theories appeared in the 1970s, 1980s and 1990s has been theories and of research different directions data base current to do problems - indexing , optimization , parallelism , transactions and of others to merge witness it has been .

All revolutions one after another done no more left _ to the object directed data model (Atkinson et al et al ., 1989), Intelligent Data databases (Zaniolo , 1992), XML data bases (Bonifati and Cuzzocrea , 2007) - one how many naming - data base community to change a promise gave , but critical to the mass reached did n't go applications work exit in the market .

Big data SQL (relational) data in the environment bases main The problem is probably correct measure done increase (Jacobs , 2009). We are this statement to change preferred because we will see many SQL/relational DBMS many years during distribution and scaling for great to solutions have but they are usually license for great hardware and big in quantity money Demand does _ So so , "SQL data bases right to scaling able not " in fact " means " cost " . the meaning means

Full extensible SQL data bases current to do is prohibited . In 2010 and 2011 , the NoSQL tsunami was almost there no from the place came _ In fact never from where wrong name. Some of the Internet giants (ie , Yahoo, Google, Amazon, Facebook, LinkedIn) are extensive scope applications for to transactions based SQL data bases (ACID - Atomicity , consistency , isolation , durability) are very fast and scaling for very expensive that determined . and as well as their in applications collected some data ACID Demand to do for not so much important

it's not was (posts , comments , comments and others). So so , relational from the model fundamentally difference who does data to the models based on new DBMSs offer done .

NoSQL is to the question answer to give of trying Big Data directly is the result : different formats collected big in volume information storage and inquiry / analysis to do for which systems the most suitable will come ? of NoSQL systems for Cattell six main technical features there is :

- A lot on servers simple of operations horizontal scale ;
- A lot nodes according to information repetition and distribution ;
- Simple call level interfaces or protocols ;
- Weaker (to ACID than) parallelism model ;
- Data storage for distributed indexes and operative from memory efficient use _
- Information to his records new attributes dynamic input _

But of NoSQL systems explosion basically above of properties economic consequences with depends on :

- NoSQL data shops very big in volume information again to work capable ;
- Information work issued to minutes very near was (webservers logs , sensors , mobile from devices) to be collected " now " . possible ;
- Openness : almost all NoSQL data shops open source and each how language (Python, Perl, Java and others) to be written to plugins tend ;
- Price : NoSQL systems most of them free ;
- NoSQL is simple or average to equipment installation possible ;
- Easier and faster work exit and placement ;
- Big and enthusiastic users and work exits communities ;
- of information openness : private data base products with In comparison , NoSQL data shops different formats import data and export to do with easy works _

Big data for traditional the infrastructure was a parallel relational DBMS if it is wide scope information analysis to do for basic NoSQL component parts are Hadoop and Map-Reduce . Hadoop and Map-Reduce mutually in relationships from colleagues fundamentally difference did without , tens years before high level relational in systems there is has been features present will (Pavlo and et al . , 2009). From this except , Hadoop/Map-Reduce and parallel/SQL systems between efficiency comparison still a lot in terms of the next one for better, the results is showing

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